

ConnectMe – A Networking and Socializing App Using Flutter and Firebase

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Abstract- In today's world, making meaningful connections with like-minded individuals has become increasingly difficult due to a lack of efficient platforms for real-time networking and collaboration. The ConnectMe app aims to bridge this gap by leveraging modern technologies, transforming the process of finding, connecting, and interacting with others based on shared interests such as travel, movies, treks, or other activities. The core aim of our project is to create a platform that allows users to seamlessly find individuals with similar passions and meet up with them in real-time. The traditional methods of connecting with others, like social media platforms, often lack the personalization and spontaneity needed for real-life meetups. ConnectMe addresses these issues by providing an easy-to-use mobile app built with Flutter and backed by Firebase, which enables realtime interactions. connections, notifications, and The mobile application includes features such as instant activity matching, real-time notifications, and seamless user interaction. The app employs Firebase for authentication, data management, and event notifications, while Flutter provides a crossplatform solution for mobile development.

Keywords- Flutter, Firebase, real-time interaction, social networking, SDK, instant messaging, SQL

I. INTRODUCTION

ConnectMe is a Smart Social Networking Mobile Application designed to help individuals find and connect with others who share common interests. Unlike traditional networking apps, ConnectMe simplifies and enhances the process of making meaningful connections in real-time.

It focuses on activities like travel, movies, hikes, and more, enabling users to quickly find companions for shared activities.

The application is a Hybrid Mobile Application developed using the Flutter SDK, which allows for crossplatform compatibility on both Android and iOS devices with a single codebase.

With the help of Firebase, the app offers real-time user authentication, data synchronization, and notifications, while also activitymatching algorithm incorporating.

The core features of ConnectMe include:

Activity Matching: Helps users find and connect with individuals interested in similar activities.

Real-time Notifications: Ensures users stay updated on new matches, events, and messages.

Instant Messaging: Allows users to interact instantly through chat before meeting up.

User Profiles: Let users set up personal profiles detailing their interests and preferences. In this project, we aim to explore how Flutter and Firebase can be integrated to provide a seamless and engaging platform for social interaction.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In today's fast-paced digital world, people find it increasingly difficult to establish meaningful real-life connections with individuals who share similar interests. Although social media platforms provide connectivity, they lack effective mechanisms for interest-based matching, real-time interaction and activity-oriented networking.

Most existing applications focus on virtual engagement rather than facilitating real-world meetups and collaboration. Users often struggle to:

- Find people with similar interests such as travel, movies, and trekking
- Communicate and coordinate in real-time
- Discover and participate in relevant events
- Build genuine and meaningful social connections

This gap highlights the need for an intelligent platform that enables real-time, interest-based social networking, allowing users to connect, interact, and engage in shared activities seamlessly.

Fig 1: ConnectMe – A Networking and Socializing App Using Flutter and Firebase.

Table 1: Properties of Structure.

Property	Description
Application Name	ConnectMe
Platform	Android & iOS(Cross-platform)
Framework	Flutter
Backend	Firebase
Database	Cloud Firestore(NoSQL)
Authentication	Firebase Authentication
Programming Language	Dart
IDE/Tools	Android Studio, VS Code, Firebase Console
Real-Time Messaging	Firebase Cloud Messaging & Firestore
Storage	Firebase Cloud Storage
Main Features	Activity Matching, Real-time Chat, Notifications, Event Discovery, User Profiles
Target Users	Users interested in activities like travel, movies, trekking, etc.
Update Mechanism	Real-time data synchronization using Firebase
Security	Secure authentication and encrypted data handling
Architecture Type	Three-tier (Presentation, Business Logic, Data Layer)
Development Model	Agile Methodology

II. CONCLUSION

The ConnectMe application successfully addresses the challenges of finding meaningful connections in today's digital world. It provides an efficient platform that enables users to connect based on shared interests and activities. By integrating modern technologies like Flutter and Firebase, the system ensures a seamless and responsive user experience.

The application supports real-time communication, allowing users to interact instantly and plan activities effectively. Features such as activity-based matching, event discovery, and instant messaging enhance user engagement and usability. The use of Firebase ensures secure authentication, reliable data storage, and real-time synchronization across devices.

The three-tier architecture of the system improves scalability, flexibility, and maintainability. It allows easy integration of new features and smooth system updates. The application also ensures data security and privacy, which are critical aspects of modern mobile applications.

Overall, ConnectMe provides a smart and innovative solution for social networking by focusing on real-world interactions rather than just virtual connections. It simplifies the process of discovering people, organizing events, and building meaningful relationships.

Thus, the system proves to be efficient, user-friendly, and suitable for enhancing social connectivity in a modern environment.

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